

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF METHODS USED IN EVALUATION OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Annotation: *In this study, the author's comments are given according to the analysis of scientific sources devoted to the assessment of innovative activities of commercial banks.*

Keywords: *commercial bank, innovative activity, results of innovative activity, methodology of evaluation of innovative activity, multifactor analysis.*

Introduction

To analyze the activities of commercial banks and its specific areas many mathematical models and methods are used. In general, non-parametric methods of assessing the effectiveness of banking activities include a network methodology based on the division of banking activities into a series of stages and performance evaluation for each of them (network DEA), a dynamic network method (network DEA) that takes into account time at each stage of banking activities, a weighted DEA-based methodology, a multi-criteria methodology (TOPSIS) based on minimizing the distance between the most inefficient and most efficient bank, and others are widely used. Each of them has certain advantageous and disadvantageous sides.

The main part

In this work, we try to analyze the scientific sources for evaluating the effectiveness of innovative activities of commercial banks. The main focus will be on some researches published during 2021.

E. I. Alexina's research work "Development of forms and methods of stimulating innovation in modern conditions" is based on the assumption that the development of the system of stimulating innovation leads to an increase in innovation, resulting in the development of regions and / or sectors of the economy.

Hypothesis which is given above was made in two stages:

In the first stage, the impact of innovative activities on the development of the country's economy was analyzed;

In the second stage, the system of financial incentives assessed the effectiveness of innovative activities and their impact on economic development.

According to the end of analysis, in our opinion, the scientist noted two important conclusions: firstly, there is a moderate correlation between the indicators of regional GDP per capita and the volume of innovation activity, as well as the low level of impact of developed technologies on macroeconomic indicators; secondly, the cost of innovative activities shows its positive result only after 3 years.

According to the research conducted by E. I. Alexina, the following can be noted:

Firstly, the effectiveness of innovative activities depends on the level of socio-economic development of the country's territory and / or economic sector. Thus, the priorities of banking reform and their successful implementation, the strategy of innovative development of banks and the results of its implementation, the formed corporate culture, organizational structure of management and etc. are the main factors determining the effectiveness of innovative activities;

Secondly, the technologies, products and services obtained as a result of innovative activities are not immediately effective. This shows that investments in this area should be directed to strategic development points. This means that innovation activity for banks should be focused on the implementation of clearly defined goals and the formation of innovation infrastructure based on this aim;

Thirdly, the organization of innovative activities depends primarily on the level of provision of highly qualified specialists. Moreover, there should be a special structure for the practical implementation of the created innovations. Both of these areas require competencies outside of the bank's specialization.

Thus, the organization of innovative activities in banks:

a) increase in the number of bank employees with specialists in the field of information technology;

b) new requirements (for the acquisition of technological competencies) for higher education institutions.

According to the results of the analysis of innovative activities of commercial banks in the research work "Methodological features of the organization of effective innovative activities of commercial banks" prepared by TA Timkina, the analytical methods used in modern practice are market instruments of banking, taking into account digital transformation, innovative products and services. concluded that it does not provide an opportunity to evaluate its effectiveness.

This methodology proposed by the author can be classified as a unique combination of mathematical modeling and survey methodology. This methodology should be used in the development of proposals and recommendations on a number of important issues of banking, in particular innovation. At the same time, in this methodology, the possibilities of assessing the mechanisms of the relationship between the current state of banking, development strategy and changes in the external environment are somewhat limited.

Conclusions and suggestions

The conclusions, scientific proposals and practical recommendations formed through the analyzed scientific sources have certain shortcomings, despite their theoretical and methodological significance in terms of the organization of innovative activities, evaluation of results. These include:

Firstly, the result of innovative activity cannot be achieved quickly. Any innovative products and services will begin to bear their economic effect over time. The use of current period indicators in determining economic efficiency leads to a distortion of the real situation. In this regard, in our opinion, it is expedient to evaluate the effectiveness of the indicators set out in the strategic development (or innovative development strategy);

Secondly, the effectiveness of innovative activities depends in many respects on the success of economic reforms in the country, the state of the training system and other macroeconomic factors. It is not possible to take these factors into account in the proposed methodology;

Thirdly, the development of innovative developments and technologies takes a certain amount of time. During this time, perfect and / or inexpensive technologies may emerge in the innovative market relative to the consequence of the project planned to be produced. In this case, innovative projects will have to be stopped. The costs incurred are accounted for as an expense to the entity. But one of the most vital aspects of the work done on the innovative project is shaping the innovative experience. This cannot be expressed in financial terms.

The analysis of the above scientific sources shows that it is expedient to use the survey methodology to assess the effectiveness of organizational mechanisms of innovative activity in commercial banks.

In our opinion, this survey should be aimed at three groups of bank employees:

Group 1. The bank's management is directly responsible for the development and implementation of the banking development strategy.

Group 2. Employees responsible for the introduction of innovative developments in banking.

Group 3. Employees of the bank's front, back and midfielders.

The development of the questionnaire should take into account the powers and responsibilities of those working in each group, the degree of involvement in innovative activities and other factors.

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